

Creative Utilization of Fabric Waste for the Production of Infant Clothing Articles for Family Economic Sustainability in Clothing Usage

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Abstract

This study examined the clothing needs of infants that will determine the creative utilization of fabrics waste to produce infant clothing articles for family economic sustainability in clothing usage. Specifically, it identified various infant activities that involves the use of clothing articles that dictates what they wear; infant clothing articles that could be produced using fabric waste and patchwork technique and the production of infant clothing articles using fabric waste and patchwork technique. A survey design was used for the study. Population was 15, 269 mothers that registered for post-natal care in government hospitals in Rivers State. Multi-stage sampling technique and purposive sampling was used to select a sample size of 378 respondents. Questionnaire titled "infant clothing article need assessment instrument for mothers" (ICANAIM) was used for data collection. Internal consistency of instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha which yielded as follows: infant activities that involves the use of clothing = 0.92; infant clothing articles that could be produced using textile fabric waste and patchwork technique = 0.97. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings revealed ten infant activities that involves the use of clothing articles. These include playing (3.87 ± 0.97); vomiting occasionally (3.80 0.95); eating, (3.73 0.93) among others. Fourteen infant clothing articles that could be produced using fabric waste and patchwork technique. These include infant garment (4.00 0.00); bed sheet (4.00 0.00); Bib (3.87) and the production of five infant clothing articles for dressing, eating, and sleeping. The infant clothing articles produced include: a unisex dress, gown, diaper bag, bib and foam cover. Recommendations for schools to carry out more practical work and activities on creative and innovative utilization of fabric waste.

Keywords: *Infant-clothing, Fabric Waste, Economic Sustainability, Clothing production*

Introduction

To care for an infant, certain infant clothing articles are needed. These clothing articles should be suitable as the necessities that must be provided for infants. To make clothing articles comfortable and suitable the needs of infants must be considered before production. Afroza (2018) established that mothers consider comfort, safety, warmth, durability, maintenance, and cost when providing clothing for infants. Mckinley (2018) added that comfort and safety are an important factor to consider when

designing, producing, and selecting infant clothing. In designing infant clothing articles, the designer needs more concentration on comfort, safety, simplicity, and new look in designing infant clothing article.

Ayim (2018) defined production as the way fabric is being converted into a garment or any other finished product in a manufacturing system. Production of garment or any finished product involves the design or sketching of the product, production of pattern or template, cutting

and sewing. These design process will be utilized in the production and designing of infant clothing articles.

Infant clothing articles are items of clothing made for infants. These clothing articles are used to protect infants against, sun, rain and other environmental hazards as well as for adornment. Infant's clothing articles include garments, bed covers, receiving blanket, hat, cot bumpers, duvet, bib, diaper bag, burp cloth, protective panties, jacket, and toys. The demand for infant clothing is on the increase as long as people have babies, (Kleinhuckelkotten and Neitzke, 2019). The market for infant clothing is sustainable with growth expansion. The production cost of producing infant clothing articles with fabric waste utilizes patchwork technique, this technique reduces the cost of infant clothing articles in the market. Also, beautiful infant clothing article designed with patchwork will be created and launched into the market. The use of fabric waste is eco-friendly as it reduces environmental waste created as well as enhances family economic sustainability.

According to United Nations (1987) in Ezema (2017) sustainability is defined as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising those of the future. In fashion, sustainability refers to clothing and accessories that are designed, produced and sold in an environmentally friendly and eco-conscious way. (Annamma and Camilo, 2017). Davidson (2021) defined sustainable fashion as clothing that is produced in a responsible way that supports the earth to sustain itself. According to Tailor (2016) the four pillars of sustainability are social, human environmental and economic sustainability. Economic sustainability implies a system of production that satisfies present consumption levels without compromising future needs (Lobo, Pietriga and Appert, 2015). Economic sustainability aims to maintain the capital intact and improve the standard of living. In fashion, it refers to the efficient reuse of clothing articles to avoid fabric waste creation. Therefore, designers can reuse materials, recycle, upcycle, repair and remodel garment and recreate existing design concept.

Fabric waste refers to fabrics that are thrown away or set aside as worthless in garment construction centers. According to Clark (2018) and Brinkmann (2018) fabric wastes are the cut-offs or scraps from fabrics found in garment production centers. Fabric waste are resources that are abundant in every clothing construction centers, yet these valuable resources are wasted due mainly to poor economic knowledge, poor creativity and innovative ideas, poor entrepreneurial skills, and inability to see opportunities in the environment. Fabric wastes are considered as waste in many clothing constructions centers, but these wastes could serve as an enormous source of income generation for clothing entrepreneurs. This is because useful clothing articles could be produced from them.

Clothing entrepreneurs that are creative and innovative can utilize and design fabric waste into excellent and useful finished infant products. The opportunities that lie in production of infant clothing articles are real and ever present as market of infant clothing is growing significantly (Custom Market Research Services, 2017 -2025 forecast). There is a huge market for infant clothing articles as mothers value clothing crafts and are very ready to spend money on clothing articles to adorn especially creative clothing. Production of infant clothing article is a lucrative business not just in Nigeria but also in the world at large. With creativity, sustainable clothing innovation can be done through the utilization of fabric waste and patchwork technique.

Creativity is an activity that involves discovering, evaluating and exploiting opportunities to introduce new goods and services. Gholami and Karime (2014) view it in relation to divergent thinking as a way of solving problems and convergent thinking as a way of obtaining correct answers to a problem. Through creativity, ideas that are new and potentially useful in providing innovation and profitability in clothing can be utilized for sustainable clothing innovation through various sewing techniques which include patchwork.

Patchwork is a sewing technique in which small pieces of fabrics in different designs, colors or textures are sewn together. According to Wickell (2019) patchwork also referred to as pieced work is a form of needle work that involves sewing together pieces of fabric into a large design. The larger design is usually based on repeating patterns built up with different fabric shapes. These shapes are carefully measured and cut into basic geometric shapes making it easy to piece together. Patchwork can be used to make apparel, household clothing articles as well as infant clothing articles.

In Rivers State, a lot of clothing construction centers exist as small-scale businesses and provides employment opportunities for individuals and families. These clothing construction centers generate huge amount of fabric waste. Fabric waste generated from clothing construction centers in Rivers State are heaped in the shops and are littered in surroundings as waste. These fabric wastes are sometimes thrown away into drainages and cause blockage in drainages resulting to some of the flooding challenges experienced in Rivers State. Also, these waste fabrics are sometimes burnt as a means of evacuation. Burning fabric waste result to environmental pollution, health hazard as well as soil degradation. This fabric waste that are generated by clothing construction centers and are abandoned and thrown away as worthless can be joined together to obtain required length and width using patchwork technique to produce useful infant clothing articles.

The production cost of infant clothing articles with fabric waste utilizing patchwork technique will reduce thereby reducing the cost of infant clothing articles in the market. Hence a need to examine the clothing needs of infants that will determine the creative utilization of textile fabrics waste to produce infant clothing articles which will contribute to family economic sustainability in clothing usage in Rivers State.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study was to undertake creative utilization of fabrics

waste to produce infant clothing articles for family economic sustainability. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. identify infant activities that involves the use of clothing articles that dictates what they wear in River's state
2. determine infant clothing articles that could be produced using fabric waste through patchwork technique for family economic sustainability in clothing usage in River's state.
3. Produce infant clothing articles using the patch work technique

Methodology

Design of the Study

The design of the study is a survey design and research and development, survey research was used to respond to objective one and two while research and development was used in the production of the patch work articles. River's state has a good number of clothing construction centers that operates as small and medium industries that produces waste fabrics and there is a huge market for infant clothing, sourcing for the waste fabrics cuts was done from these clothing construction centers.

Population for the Study

The population for the study comprised 15,269 mothers with infants (post-natal record from government owned hospital in Rivers State, 2020).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for the study was 378 respondents (mothers with infants). The 378 mothers that made up the sample size was drawn using krejcie and Morgan table for determining sample size. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select sample size for mothers. In the first stage, the 23 Local government Areas in Rivers State was zoned into three senatorial zones. In the second stage, three LGAs were randomly selected from each of the senatorial zone. In the third stage, three communities were randomly selected from the nine LGAs given a total of 27 communities. In the fourth stage, 2

government hospitals were selected from the 27 communities given a total of 54 hospitals. In the fifth stage, 7 mothers were randomly selected from the 54 hospitals each given a total of 378 mothers.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed based on the specific objectives of the study. The questionnaire was titled "Infant Clothing Article Need Assessment Instrument for Mothers (ICANAIM)". The questionnaire was divided into two sections A and B. Section A contained demographic information of the respondents. Section B had four-point scales measuring 11 infant activities that involves use of clothing articles; 14 infant clothing article that could be produced using fabric waste and patchwork techniques. The response options were based on a 4 - point Gothman rating scale comprising; Strongly Agreed (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

The mothers were visited during their post-natal visit in the hospital. At such visits,

378 copies of the infant clothing article need assessment instrument for mothers (ICANAIM) were distributed with the help of five research assistants. All the 378 copies were retrieved showing 100% return rate.

Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained for the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Mean of 2.50 was used as cut-off point for decision making for the four-point scale of each (ICANAIM) items. Any item with mean rating of 2.50 and above was considered as agreed while any mean value below 2.50 was considered disagreed. All data collected were analyzed using statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) version 25.0.

Result

The data in Table 1 below revealed that the mean value of 10 infant activities that involves the use of clothing articles that dictates what they wear ranged from 3.87 - 3.14 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50 (>2.50).

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Mothers on Infant Activities that Involves the Use of Clothing Articles that Dictates what they wear in Rivers state.

RESPONDENTS

MOTHERS = 378			
Infant Activities	Mean	Std	Remark
Eating/ messing up with food	3.73	0.93	A
Sleeping	3.60	0.90	A
Bathing	3.67	0.92	A
Relaxing	3.14	0.87	A
Sitting up/toddling	3.46		A
Crawling	3.40	0.85	A
Walking/Running	3.73	0.93	A
Playing (stumbling, cycling, climbing)	3.87	0.97	A
Vomiting occasionally	3.80	0.95	A
Crying	3.59	0.90	A

Table 2 reveals that the mean value of 14 items that could be produced using fabric waste and patchwork technique range from 4.00 - 3.07. The result shows that the mean value is greater than the cut-off point of 2.50

(> 2.50). This indicated that all the 14 items could be produced using fabric waste and patchwork technique for family economic sustainability in clothing usage in Rivers State. The standard deviation of the items

ranged from 1.00 - 0.77 indicating that the strength of the agreement is close and that mean responses were not far from each other.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Mothers and Tailors on infant Clothing articles that could be produced using fabric waste in Rivers state

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	Std	Remark
1	Bib	3.87	0.97	Agreed
2	Duvet	3.67	0.92	Agreed
3	Bed sheet	4.00	1.00	Agreed
4	Foam cover	3.80	0.95	Agreed
5	Infant garment	4.00	1.00	Agreed
6	Diaper bag	3.73	0.93	Agreed
7	Face towel	3.54	0.88	Agreed
8	Baby warmer	3.47	0.87	Agreed
9	Burp cloth	3.39	0.85	Agreed
10	Protective panties	3.27	0.82	Agreed
11	Hat	3.47	0.87	Agreed
12	Cot bumper	3.07	0.77	Agreed
13	Baby carrier	3.73	0.93	Agreed
14	Toys	3.53	0.88	Agreed

Fig 1: unisex over all

Fig 2: girl dress

Fig 3: Diaper bag

Fig 4: Bib

Fig 5: Foam cover

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the clothing needs of infants that will determine the creative utilization of fabrics waste to produce infant clothing articles for family economic sustainability in clothing usage in Rivers State. The study found evidence that infants are majorly involved in 14 activities that requires the use of clothing articles that dictates what they wear. These activities include eating, sleeping, bathing, playing, crawling, relaxing, vomiting and going out occasionally among others. This finding on infant activities that requires clothing articles conforms with the findings of Gurevich (2019) who stated that infants are playful and active in various activities such as playing, crawling, eating, crying, sleeping and other physical activities. The findings of this study also corroborate that of McKinley (2018) who established that infants are constantly involved in a range of activities that requires clothing articles and that infants should be dressed to suit the activities (sleeping, eating, playing, outing) and temperature of their surroundings.

The study with respect to research question two showed that all the infant clothing articles that could be produced using fabric waste and patchwork technique identified in the study are basic items for infant use and care. These infant clothing articles include bib, burp cloth, toys, foam cover, bedsheet, infant garment, diaper bag, hat, cot bumper among others. This finding is in line with that of Kaur and Kaur (2014) who asserted that fabric waste can be used to produce useful clothing articles such as hats, skirts, vest and accessories. Udeani (2017) in support of the findings asserted that fabric waste could be used to produce various useful household clothing articles such as wall hangings, table mat, table runner, braided foot mat, cushion cover among others

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that clothing needs of infants will determine the creative utilization of fabrics waste for family economic sustainability. Also, creative utilization of fabric waste will arrest the effect of environmental hazards that results from

disposing fabric waste indiscriminately. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. Home Economists should involve creativity training for entrepreneurial ship. Schools should carry out more practical work and activities with students to encourage and enlighten students on creative and innovative utilization of fabric waste.
2. Clothing production centers should see waste as wealth and should be creatively utilized waste in diverse areas for production of useful clothing articles

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